

ЕКОНОМІЧНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ГАЛУЗЕЙ ТА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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International economic activity in the conditions of economic integration

The subject of the research is theoretical and practical aspects of international economic activity in the conditions of economic integration.

The aim of the research is to define the concepts of «international economic activity» and «economic integration», to study the factors influencing international economic activity and its main goals, as well as the prerequisites for the creation of international economic integration.

Research methods. In the process of writing the article, theoretical, general scientific and special methods of defining the category of concepts international economic activity and economic integration were used.

Results of the investigation. As a result of writing the article, it was established that the formation, development and competitiveness of international economic activity in the conditions of economic integration, their influence on the formation of the global economy and integration processes are determined by the factors and evolution of internationalization, the transformation of productive forces, the impact of changes in the environment of the international sphere and the deepening of relationships between national economies at all levels of international interaction. It is proven that in the modern integration space, the development of international economic activity as a set of international actively competitive business processes carried out by national and international enterprises is due to the desire to strengthen the integration of national economies into the global integration international process. It was determined that international economic activity in modern business conditions is an integral component of the formation and further development of enterprises, the efficiency of which must be constantly improved in order to obtain maximum profit and a synergistic effect from the activation of export operations. In addition, effective integration business processes in foreign markets require flexible use of various methods and approaches to conducting international activities with forecasting fluctuations in the international market situation and analysis of the external environment.

Scope of the results. Economics, International Economics, International Economic Integration, Enterprise Management Strategy.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it was established that the key aspects of integration

transformations in international economic activity are the support of the European Union and the simplification of rules for entering international markets, increasing the scale of international trade, increasing the production process of a global product, the use of digitization and digitization in all spheres of international economic activity. It was established that among the best countries for starting an international business in 2023, the following were identified: Great Britain, Sweden, Hong Kong, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Canada, Denmark, Singapore, Australia, and Switzerland. Ukraine ranks 77th among the 161 best countries for doing business according to the Forbes rating. It was analyzed and determined that the main motivating motive of international economic activity is the commercialization of the result, and international economic activity itself in the conditions of economic integration ensures the highest level of development of the international economy, which determines the further formation and development of the global economic system.

Keywords: international economic activity, economic integration, integrated business structures, competitive advantages, business conditions, international trade.

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Міжнародна економічна діяльність в умовах економічної інтеграції

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні аспекти міжнародної економічної діяльності в умовах економічної інтеграції.

Метою дослідження є: визначення понять «міжнародна економічна діяльність» та «економічна інтеграція», дослідження чинників впливу на міжнародну економічну діяльність та основних її цілей, а також передумов створення міжнародної економічної інтеграції.

Методи дослідження. В процесі написання статті було використано теоретичні, загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи визначення категорії понять міжнародна економічна діяльність та економічна інтеграція.

Результати роботи. В результаті написання статті було встановлено, що становлення, розвиток та конкурентоспроможність міжнародної економічної діяльності в умовах економічної інтеграції, їх вплив на формування глобальної економіки та інтеграційні процеси зумовлюється чинниками та еволюцією інтернаціоналізації, трансформацією продуктивних сил, впливом зміни середовища міжнародної сфери та поглибленням взаємозв'язків між національними економіками на всіх рівнях міжнародної взаємодії. Доведено, що в сучасному інтеграційному просторі розвиток міжнародної економічної діяльності як сукупності міжнародних активно-конкурентоспроможних бізнес-процесів здійснюваних національними та міжнародними підприємствами обумовлений прагненням посилити інтеграцію національних економік у глобальний інтеграційний міжнародний процес. Визначено, що міжнародна економічна діяльність в сучасних умовах ведення бізнесу є невід'ємною складовою становлення та подальшого розвитку підприємств, ефективність якої постійно потрібно вдосконалювати для отримання максимального прибутку та синергійного ефекту від активізації експортних операцій. Крім того, ефективні інтеграційні бізнес-процеси на зовнішніх ринках вимагають гнучкого використання різних методів та підходів до ведення міжнародної діяльності із прогнозуванням коливань міжнародної кон'юнктури ринку та аналізу зовнішнього середовища.

Галузь застосування результатів. Економіка, міжнародна економіка, міжнародна економічна інтеграція, стратегія управління підприємствам.

Висновки. В результаті дослідження було встановлено, що ключовими аспектами інтеграційних перетворень в міжнародній економічній діяльності є підтримка Європейським Союзом та спрощення правил входу на міжнародні ринки, нарощування масштабів міжнародної торгівлі, збільшення процесу виробництва глобального продукту, використання діджиталізації та цифровізації в усіх сферах міжнародної економічної діяльності. Встановлено, що серед найкращих країн для запуску міжнародного бізнесу у 2023 р. визначено: Великобританію, Швецію, Гонконг, Нідерланди, Нову Зеландію, Канаду, Данію, Сінгапур, Австралію, Швейцарію. Україна займає 77-е

місце серед 161 кращих країн для ведення бізнесу за рейтингом *Forbes*. Проаналізовано та визначено, що головним стимулюючим мотивом міжнародної економічної діяльності є комерціалізація кінцевого результату, а сама міжнародна економічна діяльність в умовах економічної інтеграції забезпечує найвищий рівень розвитку міжнародної економіки, що зумовлює подальше становлення та розвиток глобальної економічної системи.

Ключові слова: міжнародна економічна діяльність, економічна інтеграція, інтегровані структури бізнесу, конкурентні переваги, умови ведення бізнесу, міжнародна торгівля.

Formulation of the problem. The formation, development and competitiveness of international economic activity in the conditions of economic integration, their impact on the formation of the global economy and integration processes is determined by the factors and evolution of internationalization, the transformation of productive forces, the impact of changes in the environment of the international sphere and the deepening of relationships between national economies at all levels of international interaction. In the modern integration space, the development of international economic activity as a set of international actively competitive business processes carried out by national and international enterprises is due to the desire to strengthen the integration of national economies into the global integration international process [1; 3; 5].

International economic activity in modern business conditions is an integral component of the formation and further development of enterprises, the efficiency of which must be constantly improved in order to obtain maximum profit and a synergistic effect from the activation of export operations. In addition, effective integration business processes in foreign markets require flexible use of various methods and approaches to conducting international activities with forecasting fluctuations in the international market situation and analysis of the external environment [2; 4; 6].

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The process of development of international economic activity in conditions of integration was studied in their works by the following foreign and domestic scientists: D. Dzhonson, S. K. Poulson, K. Terner, B. Toin, U. H. Tomlinson, S. Robokk, K. Simmonds, D. H. Luk'ianenko, S. Mochny, S. Fomishyn, Ye. H. Panchenko, O. A. Shvydanenko and others. Some aspects of the development of the implementation of international economic activity by transnational corporations in the conditions of global economic integration require special attention [1–16].

Presenting main material. International economic activity is determined by the main focus, which consists in ensuring the obtaining of permanent competitive advantages of two or more countries among competitors. The desire of national enterprises to intensify their international activities is a motive and an opportunity to realize the right to obtain competitive advantages in the process of integration changes. The key aspects of integration transformations in international economic activity are the support of the European Union and the simplification of rules for entering international markets, increasing the scale of international trade, increasing the process of global product production, the use of digitization and digitization in all spheres of international economic activity. It should be emphasized separately that international economic activity is focused on the implementation of methods and techniques for the expansion of sales markets, services, capital, labor force, the search for new sources of resources (production, financial, innovation, investment, personnel), and the implementation of deep diversification of general economic activity [7; 8; 10].

Modern dominants in the development of international economic activity are under the influence of factors (foreign and venture capital investment, international production) in relation to the entry of companies into foreign markets. The effective functioning of an international company in the conditions of integration of various forms of business relies on the strategy of realizing its competitive advantages due to internalization, reduction of transaction costs, advanced knowledge and technologies [9; 11; 12].

The presence of well-known international companies on the Ukrainian market is an indicator of Ukraine's investment attractiveness, assessment of its potential for global business, compliance of the domestic business system with generally accepted world standards (Table 1) [6; 13; 15].

Among the best countries for starting international economic activity (international business)

Table 1. Top-25, the most successful international companies in Ukraine

№	Company	Brief description
1	2	3
1.	Amway Ukraine	In 2019, the turnover of «Amway Ukraine» LLC exceeded UAH 1.4 billion, more than 200,000 independent Amway entrepreneurs in Ukraine cooperate with the company.
2.	Credit Agricole Bank	The oldest foreign bank in Ukraine, which has been operating on the market since 1993, is a strategic partner for agribusiness and the main bank for car enthusiasts.
3.	Dell Technologies	Founded in the USA in 1984, the company serves customers in 180 countries around the world, including 99% of Fortune 500 companies and individual consumers.
4.	FMC Ukraine	FMC Corporation includes 26 production facilities, 23 research laboratories and representative offices in more than 70 countries of the world. FMC came to Ukraine in 1992.
5.	Groupe SEB	Today, Groupe SEB is present in 150 countries of the world and has achieved leadership positions on all continents thanks to its extensive network and wide range of products of well-known global brands.
6.	Idea Bank	Idea Bank has been operating on the Ukrainian market since 1989, has representative offices in all regions of the country, and despite the challenges of economic crises, the bank occupies a leading position on the market in retail cash lending.
7.	Karcher	Alfred Kärcher SE&Co. KG is a German company with a turnover of 2.578 billion euros and 13.5 thousand employees, representative offices in most countries of the world, 16 subsidiaries and well-deserved authority on the market.
8.	lifecell	The operator belongs to Turkcell – a Turkish provider of converged telecom and technological services.
9.	LG	LG Electronics opened its representative office in Ukraine back in 1996 and since then has been engaged in the import of consumer electronics in Ukraine, provides information support, provides technical support and assistance to buyers.
10.	L’Oreal	The L’Oréal group is a leading global player in the field of beauty. The sales volume of the L’Oréal group in 2019 reached 29.87 billion euros, and 88,000 people work in its staff in 150 countries around the world.
11.	Mastercard	Mastercard is a global technology company operating in the payment industry. The company unites consumers in more than 210 countries and territories of the world. The Mastercard representative office in Ukraine was opened in 2006.
12.	Microlife	The Microlife company is a world leader in the development and production of medical diagnostic equipment for use at home and in medical institutions.
13.	Nestlé	Nestlé is one of the world’s largest companies in the field of food and beverage production, represented in 187 countries, and 300,000 employees around the world work to achieve a common goal.
14.	PepsiCo Ukraine	PepsiCo is one of the largest producers of food and beverages in Ukraine. Over the years of work in Ukraine, the company has become one of the largest investors in the economy and taxpayers in the budget.
15.	Radisson Hotels	Radisson Hotel Group is the first international hotel chain that is represented on the territory of Ukraine. The company’s portfolio includes seven different brands and more than 1,400 hotels in operation and under construction around the world.
16.	Royal Canin	Royal Canin, a global innovator in the field of healthy pet nutrition, has been developing pet foods for their diverse needs for 50 years.
17.	SOCAR Energy Ukraine	SOCAR Energy Ukraine is a subsidiary of the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The representative office of SOCAR in Ukraine was opened in 2008 and already has 55 gas stations in 11 regions of Ukraine.
18.	TUI Ukraine	TUI Ukraine is one of the leading tour operators operating under the European brand since 2009. It includes more than 260 agencies of its own retail network and franchising.
19.	Visa	Visa is not just one of the leaders of the payments market, the company is working on increasing the share of non-cash payments in the consumer and business segments.
20.	«Gedeon Richter»	Hungarian pharmaceutical company founded in 1901 is represented on five continents by six subsidiaries and joint ventures, 29 representative offices and 40 commercial and marketing companies.
21.	«Innotek International Laboratory»	«Innotek International Laboratory» is a French family pharmaceutical company whose products are sold in more than 100 countries around the world.
22.	Mareven Food Europe	The company «Mareven Food Europe» with 100% Vietnamese–Japanese capital is one of the largest manufacturers of fast food and culinary products on the market of Ukraine.
23.	McDonald’s	This company was a pioneer of global business in all countries that opened up to the world, and Ukraine was no exception.
24.	Renault Ukraine	In 2000, the Renault brand began its activities in Ukraine. Today, the Renault company has 35 dealerships in the largest cities of our country, where more than 1,000 people work.
25.	Zeppelin Ukraine	ZEPPELIN GmbH is a German industrial concern represented in 20 countries around the world as a dealer and manufacturer of various equipment.

Table 2. The best countries for doing international business in 2023

No.	Country	Characteristics
1	2	3
1.	Great Britain	In terms of ease of starting a business in the report of the Doing Business agency out of 190 countries of the world, Great Britain ranks 8th, and 3rd in Europe. Unemployment in the state is kept at the level of 4.9%, and inflation is about 0.3%.
2.	Sweden	In the Doing Business report, the country ranks 10th. The most promising industry for investment is information technology and innovation. Stockholm is considered one of the world leaders in launching startup companies.
3.	Hong Kong	Hong Kong ranks 3rd in the Doing Business report. It is the most important financial and logistics center not only of Asia, but also of the world. A free economy, an efficient tax system, investor protection and many other positive aspects make Hong Kong one of the best places to do business.
4.	The Netherlands	Despite the fact that the Netherlands ranks only 42nd in the Doing Business ranking, foreigners invest huge amounts of money in local companies, both in the field of industry and agriculture.
5.	New Zealand	In the Doing Business report, New Zealand ranks 1st. It is possible to carry out business immigration to New Zealand with the help of special programs for foreign entrepreneurs. In New Zealand, corruption and administrative pressure from the authorities are minimized.
6.	Canada	The Doing Business study ranked Canada 23rd. About 75% of Canadian exports go to the United States, on trade with which the welfare of the country as a whole largely depends.
7.	Denmark	The second representative of Scandinavia in the list of the best countries for business is Denmark. In the Doing Business rating, the country deservedly took 4th place, and 1st in Europe. Thanks to high social standards, a developed economy and clear laws, Denmark is one of the happiest countries in the world.
8.	Singapore	In the Doing Business rating, Singapore is in 2nd place after New Zealand. It has a very favorable investment climate, low tax rates, ideal infrastructure and a developed economy. The spheres of finance, information technologies and the tourism industry stand out in particular.
9.	Australia	Australia is ranked 14th in the Doing Business report. One of the main incentives for doing business in Australia is an effective tax system and the widest range of areas for investment – from agriculture to information technology.
10.	Switzerland	In the Doing Business report, the country took 36th place. The country has a very high standard of living, a transparent legal system and a prosperous economy. Competent actions of the government ensure the stability of the local currency and reliably protect the financial system of Switzerland.

in 2023 are: Great Britain, Sweden, Hong Kong, Netherlands, New Zealand, Canada, Denmark, Singapore, Australia, Switzerland (Table 2) [6; 14; 16].

It should be noted that Ukraine ranks 77th among the 161 best countries for doing business in the Forbes rating. The Central African Republic, Congo and Guinea-Bissau close the list. The owners of the world's largest economies, the United States and China, ranked 17th and 49th, respectively. Economic integration regarding the conduct of international economic activities and the investment of resources of any investment company depends on a number of factors, such as: immigration laws and requirements for business entities from abroad; taxation mechanism; trade transparency; state and level of corruption; the degree of infrastructure development and digitization; politi-

cal stability and security; development of innovative technologies and innovations; state of security and qualification of workers [1–6].

At the same time, the main motivating motive of international economic activity is the commercialization of the result. This motive is realized through the search and establishment of a connection with an object that is able to provide it with the necessary resources. Therefore, this process should be interpreted as the activity of subjects of individuals, corporations, other institutional associations aimed at finding, gaining influence, changing or creating objects capable of providing the resources necessary to maintain a state of dynamic equilibrium with the external environment of development in within the limits of integration processes (Fig. 1).[1; 4; 6–9].

Figure. 1. Stimulating motive of international economic activity in the process of economic integration [2–5]

Therefore, economic integration is an objective process of developing sustainable long-term economic ties between countries that are close in socio-economic level. Economic integration is the process of economic interaction of countries with the aim of achieving certain advantages in mutual trade of goods, services, movement of production factors by concluding interstate agreements on their further cooperation. Prerequisites for the creation of integrated business structures in international economic activity include: correlation between the levels of economic development and the degree of market maturity of the countries; geographical proximity of the countries, the presence of a common border, historically formed economic ties; presence of common economic, social, political and other aspects; manifestation of the positive consequences of countries joining already existing integrated business structures; the manifestation of negative consequences for countries that are not part of a certain integrated business structure, due to the reorientation of the economic ties of the participating countries and the absence of preferential conditions for cooperation [1–4].

At the same time, the main characteristic features of economic integration are taken into account:

- interconnection and interpenetration of national production processes;

- development of international specialization and cooperation in production, investment, innovation spheres;

- structural changes in the economy of the participating countries in accordance with the strategic goals of integration;

- purposeful regulation of the integration process, coordination of the economic strategy of the participating countries [1–4].

The general goals of international integrated business structures are not clearly described, and that is why, based on the study of the peculiarities of their activities, we will single out the following goals of international economic integration:

Achieving such goals as using the advantages of economies of scale based on expanding the capacity of national markets, reducing transaction costs, and attracting foreign investment is characteristic of the integration clusters of Africa and Central America.

Formation of a favorable foreign policy environment by strengthening mutual understanding and cooperation of the participating countries in the political, military, social and other non-economic spheres inherent in the integration clusters of the countries of Southeast Asia and the Middle East.

Increasing the efficiency of regulation of foreign trade cooperation is characteristic of the integration clusters of North, Latin America and Southeast Asia.

Activation of international investment, scientific and technical cooperation with developed countries for the structural prerequisite of the economies of the participating countries is typical for the countries of the European Union.

Supporting the development of branches of national industry through the creation of a larger regional market is the key goal of the integration clusters of the countries of Latin America and Africa, located south of the Sahara [1–4].

Therefore, international economic activity in the conditions of economic integration ensures the highest level of development of the international economy as a system of scientific–technological and organizational–functional connections between innovative types of entities such as business structures, cluster entities, which determines the further formation and development of the global economic system.

Conclusions

Thus, as a result, we propose to define international economic activity in modern business conditions as an integral component of the formation and further development of enterprises, the efficiency of which is constantly improved in order to obtain maximum profit and a synergistic effect from the activation of export operations. It was determined that the key aspects of integration transformations in international economic activity are the support of the European Union and the simplification of rules for entering international markets, increasing the scale of international trade, increasing the process of global product production, the use of digitization and digitization in all spheres of international economic activity. It was established that among the best countries for starting an international business in 2023, the following were identified: Great Britain, Sweden, Hong Kong, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Canada, Denmark, Singapore, Australia, and Switzerland. Ukraine ranks 77th among the 161 best countries for doing business according to the Forbes rating. It was analyzed and determined that the main motivating motive of international economic activity is the commercialization of the result, and international economic activity itself in the conditions of economic integration ensures the highest level of development of the international economy, which determines the further formation and development of the global economic system.

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ІВАНЮТА Т. М.

Економічні аспекти оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій (підприємств)

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні аспекти оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій (підприємств), в контексті дослідження цілей, випадків та обмежень щодо проведення оцінки бізнесу.

Метою статті є дослідження економічних аспектів оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій (підприємств), а саме аналіз цілей, випадків та обмеження щодо проведення оцінки бізнесу з урахуванням вимог законодавства.

Методи дослідження. В процесі написання статті було використано теоретичні і наукові методи дослідження для узагальнення економічних аспектів оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій (підприємств), у тому числі системний й логічний, що дозволило забезпечити концептуальну єдність дослідження, метод аналізу для представлення цілей, випадків та обмежень щодо проведення оцінки бізнесу з урахуванням вимог законодавства і метод узагальнення для систематизації висновків статті.

Результати роботи. Досліджено сутність потреб в проведенні оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій в залежності від конкретного користувача. До них відносять власника і акціонера підприємства, працівника, фірму-оцінювача, державу. Проаналізовано класифікацію цілей оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій. Встановлено випадки проведення оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій відповідно до Закону України «Про оцінку майна, майнових прав і професійну оціночну діяльність в Україні». Охарактеризовано існуючі обмеження щодо проведення оцінки майна.

Галузь застосування результатів. Сфера розвитку і оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій (підприємств) в Україні з урахуванням вимог чинного законодавства.

Висновки. Отже, в результаті дослідження встановлено, що під економічними аспектами оцінки бізнесу ринкових структур і організацій можна вважати сукупність економічних засад, параметрів та чинників впливу на оцінку бізнесу, що дають змогу визначити вартість організації (підприємства) як цілісного комплексу, здатного приносити дохід всім зацікавленим особам.

Ключові слова: оцінка, бізнес, вартість, підприємство, ринок, організація, аспект.

ІВАНЮТА Т. М.

Economic aspects of business evaluation of market structures and organizations (enterprises)

The subject of the study is the theoretical aspects of business assessment of market structures